

BLOPPBUSTERS UPCT

Teaching Science and Technology
through Movie Scenes and related
Experiments

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***UPCT-Bloopbusters*: Educational project using science fiction movie scenes to teach both physics and engineering technology**

Complementary methodology to illustrate how (or how not) the laws of physics of our universe behave while having fun

Introduction

Students often perceive science as difficult
(and/or boring).

Passive learning decreases engagement.

Science fiction can increase motivation.

Project overview

- **Use of movie scenes + related experiments.**
- **Subjects: Physics I, Applied Physics, Optical Communications (three academic years).**
- **Students analyze 'bloopers' and discuss concepts.**

Project overview

Course	Subject	Number of students	Number of men	Number of women	Average age
15/16	Applied Physics	13	8	5	25.1
	Optical Communications	39	27	12	26.4
	Physics	61	33	28	23.3
16/17	Applied Physics	14	8	6	23
	Optical Communications	36	31	5	25
	Physics	54	26	28	22.5
17/18	Applied Physics	15	10	5	23
	Optical Communications	41	33	8	24.1
	Physics	67	33	34	21.8

Methodology: key steps

- 1. Show selected movie scene.**
- 2. Students identify scientific errors.**
- 3. Instructor leads debate.**
- 4. Demonstration experiment.**
- 5. Exercises linked to the scene (20% grade).**

Examples

The impossibility of sound propagation or laser visualization along the vacuum of interstellar space (Star Wars)

Examples

Species II (1998) Delay in communications when transmitting to Mars due to speed of light is finite

Examples

7. *Movie: Species 2 (1998). Scene cut: 0:02:14 to 0:03:25.*

The scene shows the crew members of a spaceship orbiting Mars having a conversation in real time — with a lag of merely a few seconds — with people at the base in Houston, on Earth. Considering that Mars is located at an average distance from our planet of, approximately, 225 millions of kilometres, how much time should the movie scene have actually taken if the laws of physics had been respected? Why?

Note that, in the scene, the crew members from the spaceship orbiting Mars address Houston on Earth twice, with the corresponding answers from the latter.

Examples

The communications between the spaceship orbiting Mars and the base on Earth are established through electromagnetic waves, which travels at the speed of light ($3 \cdot 10^8$ m/s).

Hence, the time needed to establish one-way communication should be:

$$t = \frac{\text{distance}}{\text{speed}} = \frac{225 \cdot 10^9}{3 \cdot 10^8} = 750 \text{ seconds} = 12.5 \text{ minutes}$$

Therefore, according the laws of physics and taking into account that the communication of the scene consists of two round trips undertaken by electromagnetic waves, the scene should have lasted: $4 \cdot 12.5 = \boxed{50 \text{ minutes}}$.

Evaluation Approach

Indicators:

- **Success rate (Sr)**
- **Performance rate (Pr)**
- **Data from 3 academic years (before/after methodology).**
- **Both Sr and Pr increased in all three subjects after implementation (2017–18).**

Evaluation Approach (Sr)

Student Survey

- **Strong motivation increase.**
- **Better understanding of concepts.**
- **Positive perception of experiments.**
- **Critical thinking developed.**

Strengths of the Method

- High engagement.
- Improved conceptual understanding.
- Encourages debate and critical thinking.
- Interdisciplinary flexibility.

Challenges

- **Extra class time required.**
- **Some subjects harder to adapt.**
- **Need to select appropriate scenes.**

Conclusions

- **Method improves performance / engagement.**
- **Scalable to other engineering subjects.**
- **Supports active, motivated learning.**

Thank you!

BLOOPBUSTERS UPCT

Science, technology and...Fiction?

<https://www.discovermagazine.com/what-the-mysterious-bloop-taught-us-about-antarctica-46923>

The Bloop (and the blooper)

The Call of Cthulhu (2005)

The Call of Cthulhu

The most merciful thing in the world, I think, is the inability of the human mind to correlate all its contents. We live on a placid island of ignorance in the midst of black seas of infinity, and it was not meant that we should voyage far. The sciences, each straining in its own direction, have hitherto harmed us little; but some day the piecing together of dissociated knowledge will open up such terrifying vistas of reality, and of our frightful position therein, that we shall either go mad from the revelation or flee from the deadly light into the peace and safety of a new dark age.

— H. P. Lovecraft